

The Essence of Coq as a Formal System

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Abstract

This short text introduces the essence of Coq as a formal system. It does not attempt (in its current form) to introduce the features necessary to use Coq for real work. Prerequisite knowledge: basic programming.

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1 Motivation

Our research goal is to *prove* certain properties of certain kinds of programs, i.e. to establish beyond a reasonable doubt that these properties hold for these programs. But when have we established something beyond a reasonable doubt?

A very rigorous way to address this issue is to use a mechanised proof system: if we can express the statements that we wish to prove, as well as the proofs themselves, as strings that we can input into a computer, then we can write a program that checks that a given string is a proof of a given statement.

Such programs have in fact been written; they are called proof assistants. One of the most popular proof assistants is Coq¹. In order to introduce the notion of formal logic and formal proof, in the remainder of this text we will give an introduction to the Coq proof assistant.

2 Data values and functions

In a first approximation, Coq is just a programming language. (We will see soon how this relates to formal proof.) More specifically, it is a functional programming language, not unlike Haskell or ML. In Coq, there are two kinds of values: data values (such as booleans, integers, and strings) and functions. Each value has a type; for example, the type of `true` is `bool`. There are two kinds of types: datatypes (also called *inductive types* for reasons that will become clear later) and function types. The data values are the values of the datatypes and the functions are the values of the function types.

We illustrate these concepts using the following simple example:

```
Inductive bool := true | false.
```

```
Definition negate(b: bool): bool :=  
  match b with  
    true => false  
  | false => true  
end.
```

This Coq input file defines the datatype `bool` and the constant `negate`, which is bound to a function value that takes a `bool` argument and returns its negation. A datatype definition starts with the keyword **Inductive** and lists the constructors of the datatype. The constructors of type `bool` are `true` and `false`. Each constructor of datatype `bool` yields a value of type `bool`.

Note: to make it clearer that constant `negate` is bound to a value of a function type, we can rewrite the definition to the following equivalent form:

```
Definition negate: bool -> bool :=  
  fun (b: bool) =>  
    match b with  
      true => false  
    | false => true  
end.
```

The type of `negate` is `bool -> bool`, the type of functions that take a `bool` and return a `bool`. The *lambda expression* `fun (x: T) => E` denotes the function that takes an argument `x` of type `T` and returns the value of expression `E` (that can use `x`). In the example, the function uses a **match** expression to return a different result depending on the constructor used to construct the `bool` value `b`.

To apply a function to an argument, simply write them next to each other, separated by a space:

```
Compute negate true. (* Output: = false: bool *)
```

This snippet uses the **Compute** command to evaluate the expression `negate true`, which applies function `negate` to argument `true`. If you run this command in Coq, Coq will report that the result is the value `false`, of type `bool`.

¹<http://coq.inria.fr/>

3 Parameterized constructors

Datatype constructors can be parameterized. Such constructors yield a different value for each argument sequence. For example, consider the type `byte`:

```
Inductive byte := Byte(b7 b6 b5 b4 b3 b2 b1 b0: bool).
```

```
Definition negate_byte(b: byte): byte :=  
  match b with  
    Byte b7 b6 b5 b4 b3 b2 b1 b0 =>  
      Byte  
        (negate b7) (negate b6) (negate b5) (negate b4)  
        (negate b3) (negate b2) (negate b1) (negate b0)  
  end.
```

The datatype `byte` has 256 values, all yielded by applying the single constructor `Byte` to different sequences of booleans. Function `negate_byte` uses a `match` expression to bind the arguments used to construct the `byte` value `b` to the variables `b7`, `b6`, etc.

4 Recursive datatypes

Datatype constructors can take values of the datatype being defined as arguments; that is, a datatype definition can refer to itself in its definition. This can be used to define the type of strings of bytes, as follows:

```
Inductive string := EmptyString | NonemptyString(head: byte)(tail: string).
```

```
Definition h: byte := Byte false true true false true false false false. (* hex 68 *)
```

```
Definition i: byte := Byte false true true false true false false true. (* hex 69 *)
```

```
Definition hi: string := NonemptyString h (NonemptyString i EmptyString).
```

Notice that datatype `string` appears in its own definition as the type of the second parameter of constructor `NonemptyString`. As a result, a given value of type `string` can be used to construct a larger value of type `string`. This is illustrated by the constant `hi`, which is bound to the ASCII encoding of the two letters “hi”. The string “hi” is constructed from the string “i”, which is constructed from the empty string.

Let us define a function that concatenates two strings:

```
Definition concat(s1 s2: string): string :=  
  match s1 with  
    EmptyString => s2  
  | NonemptyString b s => NonemptyString b (concat s s2)  
  end.
```

Function `concat` inspects the first string: if it is empty, the result is simply the second string. Otherwise, the result is constructed from the first byte (the head) of the first string and the concatenation of the rest (the tail) of the first string and the second string.

Unfortunately, Coq does not allow the recursive call of `concat`. To ensure that constants are well-defined, a constant cannot appear in its own definition. This rules out the following pathological definition:

```
Definition b: bool := negate b.
```

But then, how do we define the string concatenation function? The answer is that Coq provides a *fixpoint operator* `fix` `f(x: T) {struct x}: U := E` which denotes the function that takes an argument `x` of type `T` and returns the value of the expression `E` of type `U`. The difference with the lambda expression `fun (x: T) => E` is that the body `E` of the fixpoint operator may refer to itself using the name `f`. However, to ensure that the function is well-defined, `E` must perform *structural recursion* on the argument `x`, which means that `T` must be a datatype and each recursive call must descend along the structure of `x`. More

specifically, at each recursive call, the argument must be a value that was used to construct x . (Coq checks this by checking that the argument is a variable bound by a **match** expression on x .) Since each datatype value was constructed through a finite number of constructor calls, it follows that there can only be a finite number of nested recursive calls, and therefore the function always terminates and has a well-defined value.

Therefore, we can define the string concatenation function as follows:

```
Definition concat: string -> string -> string :=
  fix f(s1: string) {struct s1}: string -> string :=
  fun (s2: string) =>
  match s1 with
    EmptyString => s2
  | NonemptyString b s => NonemptyString b (f s s2)
  end.
```

Note that the expression `f s s2` should be read as `(f s) s2`: the result of calling function `f` with argument `s` is a function, which is then applied to argument `s2`. Similarly, the type `string -> string -> string` of `concat` should be read as `string -> (string -> string)`: calling `concat` with an argument of type `string` returns a function that, when itself called with an argument of type `string`, returns a value of type `string`.

Coq accepts the fixpoint expression in the body of `concat` since it performs structural recursion: the argument `s` of the recursive call `f s` was the second argument of the constructor call used to construct `s1`.

As a convenience, the fixpoint operator actually accepts multiple parameters; the `{struct x}` annotation indicates the parameter that is reduced at each recursive call. Therefore, we can write the concatenation function more concisely as follows:

```
Definition concat: string -> string -> string :=
  fix f(s1 s2: string) {struct s1}: string :=
  match s1 with
    EmptyString => s2
  | NonemptyString b s => NonemptyString b (f s s2)
  end.
```

Coq offers syntactic sugar for a definition whose body is a fixpoint expression: the **Fixpoint** command. Using this command, the definition of `concat` reduces to the following:

```
Fixpoint concat(s1 s2: string) {struct s1}: string :=
  match s1 with
    EmptyString => s2
  | NonemptyString b s => NonemptyString b (concat s s2)
  end.
```

5 Generics

A string is a sequence of bytes. The `concat` function concatenates two strings, but it doesn't actually depend on the fact that it is dealing with bytes; it would work just as well if it was dealing with a sequence of booleans, a sequence of strings, etc. Ideally, the concatenation function would be generic in the type of the elements of the sequence.

Coq supports this. We can define a generic type of sequences of elements of some type `A` as follows:

```
Inductive list(A: Type) := nil | cons(head: A)(tail: list A).
```

```
Definition hi_as_list: list byte := cons byte h (cons byte i (nil byte)).
```

The first command defines a datatype `list` which is parameterized by a type parameter `A`, and which has two constructors: `nil` constructs an empty list, and `cons` constructs a non-empty list starting with element `head` of type `A`, and whose remaining elements are given by parameter `tail`, which is itself a list with elements of type `A`.

Note: it is not strictly correct to say that `list` is a datatype; rather, `list` is a function that takes a type and returns a datatype. When this nuance is important, we will refer to the name being defined by an **Inductive** command as a *datatype constructor*. This is not to be confused with the *data value constructors* (or *constructors* for short) of a datatype (or, strictly speaking, of a datatype constructor). For example, `nil` and `cons` are the data value constructors of the datatype constructor `list`. The former construct data values (e.g. `nil bool` and `cons bool true (nil bool)`); the latter constructs datatypes (e.g. `list bool` and `list byte`).

Note that the constructors of a generic type are automatically generic themselves: `nil` and `cons` both take a value for the type parameter `A` as their first argument. This is illustrated by the definition of constant `hi_as_list`, which is bound to the representation of the text “hi” as a list of bytes instead of a value of type `string`. Its type is therefore `list byte`. Notice that both calls of constructor `cons` as well as the call of constructor `nil` take the type `byte` as their first argument.

We can now define the generic version of function `concat`, which we shall call `append`:

```
Fixpoint append(A: Type)(l1 l2: list A) {struct l1}: list A :=
  match l1 with
    nil => l2
  | cons h t => cons A h (append A t l2)
  end.
```

Notice that in a `match` expression, only the constructor arguments for explicitly declared constructor parameters are bound to variables. (It would not make much sense to also bind the type argument, since it is fixed by the type of the value being matched.)

We can check that the function works correctly by testing it:

```
Compute append bool (cons bool true (nil bool)) (cons bool false (nil bool)).
(* Output: = cons bool true (cons bool false (nil bool)): list bool *)
```

Indeed, concatenating the singleton list “true” and the singleton list “false” yields the list “true, false”.

Notice that the declaration of type parameter `A` of `append` looks just like an ordinary parameter declaration, and indeed it is: Coq considers types to be values of a special type `Type`. So, we lied above when we said there were two kinds of values (data values and functions) and two kinds of types (datatypes and function types): there is a third kind of values (types) and a third kind of types (types of types, also known as *sorts*). For now, it is sufficient to imagine that there is only the sort `Type`.

Is there also a separate type of types of types? No: since a sort is a type, its type is itself a sort: the type of `Type` is simply `Type`.²

Notice also that there is something remarkable going on in the parameter list of `append`: the *type* of parameters `l1` and `l2` depends on the *value* of parameter `A`. Recall that the type of a function that takes an argument of type `T` and returns a value of type `U` can be denoted using arrow notation as `T -> U`. This notation is not sufficient to denote the type of `append`; for that, we need the general *dependent function type* notation `forall (x: T), U`, which denotes the type of functions that take an argument of type `T` and return a result of type `U`, where the result type `U` may refer to the argument value by the name `x`. The arrow notation `T -> U` is simply syntactic sugar for `forall (x: T), U` for the case where `U` does not mention `x`. Therefore, we can rephrase the definition of `append` as follows:

```
Definition append: forall (A: Type), list A -> list A -> list A :=
  fun (A: Type) =>
  fix f(l1 l2: list A) {struct l1}: list A :=
  match l1 with
    nil => l2
  | cons h t => cons A h (append A t l2)
  end.
```

That is, `append` is a function that, when given an argument `A` of type `Type`, returns a value of type `list A -> list A -> list A`.

²This is not entirely true. There is really an infinite family of sorts `Type(0)`, `Type(1)`, ... and the type of `Type(k)` is `Type(k+1)`. However, Coq infers these indices behind the scenes, so in most situations one can imagine that there is just the sort `Type` and that the type of `Type` is `Type`.

6 Datatypes with variable parameters

Suppose that we want to perform vector computations for a 3D game. We will want to have a type of 3D vectors. However, many operations on vectors can easily be made generic in the number of dimensions. Ideally, we would have a single library that offered vectors of any size. Still, we want to be able to distinguish between vectors of different dimensions in the types of our functions.

In Coq, this can be achieved. First, we define the type `nat` of natural numbers. A natural number is either zero or the successor of another natural number.

```
Inductive nat := zero | succ(n: nat).
```

```
Definition one: nat := succ zero.
```

```
Definition two: nat := succ one.
```

```
Definition three: nat := succ two.
```

Then, we define the type `vector`, as follows:

```
Inductive vector(A: Type): nat -> Type :=  
  empty_vector: vector A zero  
| nonempty_vector: forall (n: nat), A -> vector A n -> vector A (succ n).
```

```
Definition vector2d(A: Type): Type := vector A two.
```

```
Definition vector3d(A: Type): Type := vector A three.
```

The definition of `vector` is reminiscent of the definition of the generic type `list`: it has a type parameter `A` denoting the element type, and it has two constructors: one for the empty case, and one for the nonempty case. However, there are some differences. First of all, the result type (the type specified after the colon) of the datatype constructor and the result types of the data value constructors are specified explicitly. In earlier examples of datatype definitions, we omitted these. The result type of a datatype constructor defaults to `Type`. The result type of a data value constructor defaults to the datatype being defined. For example, writing these types explicitly for datatype `nat` would yield the following definition:

```
Inductive nat: Type := zero: nat | succ(n: nat): nat.
```

or, equivalently:

```
Inductive nat: Type := zero: nat | succ: nat -> nat.
```

The second novelty in the definition of datatype `vector` is that the result type of `vector` is not `Type` but `nat -> Type`. In general, the result type of a datatype constructor must be of the form `A1 -> ... -> An -> Type`. This form of the definition declares `n` *variable parameters* of the datatype, of types `A1`, ..., `An`. In contrast, the parameters declared using `(x: A)` notation are called the *fixed parameters*. Type `vector` has one fixed parameter, `A`, of type `Type`, and one variable parameter, unnamed, of type `nat`. As a result, to construct a datatype, `vector` must be applied to a type and a value of type `nat`.

The difference between a fixed datatype parameter and a variable datatype parameter is as follows: in the types of the data values constructed by the data value constructors, the value for the fixed parameters is the same for all constructors. For example, in the definition of `vector`, both `empty_vector` and `nonempty_vector` construct data values of type `vector A ...`. To use another value for the fixed parameter would be an error. In contrast, the values for the variable parameters may differ among constructors. For example, `empty_vector` constructs data values of type `vector A zero` whereas `nonempty_vector` constructs data values of type `vector A (succ n)` for some `n`.

Notice furthermore that the type of `nonempty_vector` is a dependent type: the constructor takes three arguments, and the type of the third argument, as well as the return type, depend on the first argument `n`.

We can now define our vector computation library, with functions that are polymorphic in the size of the vector, but whose type nonetheless specifies the incoming and outgoing vector sizes. Function `negate_vector` below illustrates this:

```
Fixpoint negate_vector(n: nat)(v: vector bool n) {struct v}: vector bool n :=  
  match v in vector _ N return vector bool N with
```

```

    empty_vector => empty_vector bool
  | nonempty_vector m b w => nonempty_vector bool m (negate b) (negate_vector m w)
end.

```

Compute

```

negate_vector two
  (nonempty_vector bool one false
   (nonempty_vector bool zero true
    (empty_vector bool))).
(* Output:
   = nonempty_vector bool one true
     (nonempty_vector bool zero false
      (empty_vector bool))
   : vector bool two *)

```

The idea of function `negate_vector` is simple: for a given `n`, `negate_vector n` takes a vector of booleans of size `n` and returns a copy of that vector with each element negated. The implementation, too, is a straightforward recursive one. The only remarkable elements of this function are the `in` and `return` clauses of the `match` expression. These aid Coq in checking the well-typedness of the `match` expression. In the simple case, when type-checking a `match` expression, Coq type-checks each case and then checks that all cases return the same type; finally, it then uses this type as the type of the `match` expression itself. For the `match` expression in `negate_vector`, this does not work: the return type of the first case is `vector bool zero`; the return type of the second case is `vector bool (succ m)` for some `m`. These are different types, so the straightforward check would fail.

To type-check the `match` expression in `negate_vector`, Coq should take into account the fact that the value being matched against is of type `vector bool n`, and that if this value is `empty_vector bool`, then `n` must equal `zero`, and that if this value is `nonempty_vector bool m b w`, then `n` must equal `succ m`, and that therefore the return type of both cases equals `vector bool n`. In other words, the `match` expression's return type depends on the value for the variable parameter in the type of the value being matched against. The `in` and `return` clauses of the `match` expression make this dependency explicit, enabling Coq to type-check the expression. Specifically, the `in` clause assigns names to the values for the variable parameters in the type of the value being matched against; the `return` clause can use these names to specify the return type of the `match` expression. When type-checking each case, the case's return expression is type-checked against the specified return type, after substituting the variable arguments in the constructor's type for the placeholder names. The type of the entire `match` expression is the specified return type, after substituting the variable arguments in the type of the expression being matched against for the placeholder names.

7 Types are propositions

In Coq, not all types are *inhabited*, i.e. for some types, there is no value of that type. For example, it is perfectly legal to declare an inductive datatype with zero constructors:

```
Inductive empty_type :=.
```

There is no value of this type; it is *uninhabited*.

The inhabitedness or uninhabitedness of a given type is not always immediately obvious. We have the following properties:

- A datatype is inhabited iff³ it has at least one constructor whose parameter types are inhabited (taking into account any dependencies between the parameters).
- A non-dependent function type is inhabited iff the parameter type is uninhabited or the return type is inhabited. (A function type whose parameter type is uninhabited has a value: the empty function.)

³if and only if

- A dependent function type is inhabited iff, for each value of the parameter type, the corresponding return type is inhabited.

Notice that these properties of the inhabitedness of Coq types are very similar to the properties of the truth of logical statements (or *propositions*). Indeed, the non-dependent function types correspond exactly to the logical implications: an implication $P \rightarrow Q$ is true iff P is false or Q is true. Furthermore, the dependent function types correspond exactly to universal quantification: `forall (x: T), U` is true iff for each value x of type T , U is true.

We can easily encode the other logical connectives as datatype constructors:

```
Inductive And(P Q: Type) := and_(p: P)(q: Q).
Inductive Or(P Q: Type) := or_left(p: P) | or_right(q: Q).
Inductive Exists(T: Type)(P: T -> Type) := exists_(t: T)(p: P t).
Inductive Equals(A: Type)(a: A): A -> Type := equals_: Equals A a a.
Inductive False :=.
Inductive True := true_.
```

Indeed, type `And P Q` is inhabited iff P is inhabited and Q is inhabited; type `Or P Q` is inhabited iff P is inhabited or Q is inhabited; `Exists T P` is inhabited iff there exists a value t of type T such that $P t$ is inhabited; `Equals A a b` is inhabited iff a equals b ; `False` is uninhabited; `True` is inhabited.

We can encode negation as follows:

```
Definition Not(P: Type) := P -> False.
```

Indeed, `Not P` is inhabited iff P is uninhabited.

Using this trick (known as the *Curry-Howard correspondence*) we can encode some properties of the functions that we have defined above as Coq types:

```
forall (b: bool), Equals bool (negate (negate b)) b
forall (s: string), Equals string (concat s EmptyString) s
```

8 Expressions are proofs

If inhabitedness of a type in Coq corresponds to truth of a proposition in logic, then what is the Coq equivalent of a logical proof? Proving the truth of a proposition corresponds to proving the inhabitedness of a type. The latter can be done by showing a witness, i.e. a value of the type. In fact, it is sufficient to show a Coq expression of the type: since evaluation of Coq expressions always terminates and never crashes, every expression of some type evaluates to a value of that type.

Let's see what this means for the various logical connectives discussed above. For an implication $P \rightarrow Q$, a proof is a function that takes an argument of type P (i.e. a proof of proposition P) and computes a value of type Q ; in other words, in order to prove $P \rightarrow Q$, it is sufficient to prove Q assuming P . Similarly, for a universal quantification `forall (x: T), P`, a proof is a function that, for any given value x of type T , computes a proof of P (where x may appear in P).

Conversely, an implication $P \rightarrow Q$ that is available as an assumption in a proof can be used to prove the goal by applying its proof to a proof of P , thus obtaining a proof of Q . Similarly, when given a proof of a universal quantification `forall (x: T), P`, applying the proof to a value of type T yields a proof of P with that value substituted for x .

As a concrete example, let's prove the proposition `forall (P Q: Type), P -> (P -> Q) -> Q`. In words: for any two propositions P and Q , if we have P and we have that P implies Q , then we have Q . The proof is very simple:

```
Definition modus_ponens: forall (P Q: Type), P -> (P -> Q) -> Q :=
fun (P Q: Type) =>
fun (p: P) =>
fun (pq: P -> Q) =>
  pq p.
```

The proof computes a value of type Q by applying the given function of type $P \rightarrow Q$ to the given value of type P , thus proving the inhabitedness of Q .

To prove a conjunction $\text{And } P \ Q$, one applies the constructor `and_` to a proof of P and a proof of Q ; similarly, to prove a disjunction $\text{Or } P \ Q$, one either applies the constructor `or_left` to a proof of P , or one applies the constructor `or_right` to a proof of Q . To prove an existential quantification $\text{Exists } T \ P$, one applies the constructor `exists_` to a *witness* t and a proof of $P \ t$.

Conversely, when given a proof of a conjunction $\text{And } P \ Q$, one can obtain a proof of P and a proof of Q using a `match` expression on the proof of $\text{And } P \ Q$; similarly, when given a proof of a disjunction $\text{Or } P \ Q$, and when proving a goal G , one can obtain a proof of G in the form of a `match` expression on the proof of $\text{Or } P \ Q$ that in the first branch proves G from P and in the second branch proves G from Q . When given a proof of an existential quantification $\text{Exists } T \ P$, one can extract a witness t and a proof of $P \ t$ through a `match` expression.

We illustrate this with a proof of the distributivity of conjunction over disjunction:

```

Definition distr: forall (P Q R: Type), And P (Or Q R) -> Or (And P Q) (And P R) :=
fun (P Q R: Type) =>
fun (pqr: And P (Or Q R)) =>
match pqr with
  and_ p qr =>
    match qr with
      or_left q =>
        or_left (And P Q) (And P R) (and_ P Q p q)
    | or_right r =>
        or_right (And P Q) (And P R) (and_ P R p r)
    end
end.

```

To prove an equality $\text{Equals } A \ a \ b$, one simply applies the constructor `equals_` $A \ a$, provided that Coq can reduce a and b to the same expression. To illustrate this, consider the property

```
forall (b: bool), Equals bool (negate (negate b)) b
```

The following proof attempt fails:

```

Definition negate_negate: forall (b: bool), Equals bool (negate (negate b)) b :=
fun (b: bool) =>
  equals_ bool b.
(* Fails *)

```

This is because Coq cannot reduce `negate (negate b)`; to reduce the `match` expression in the body of `negate`, Coq needs to know the value of b . Therefore, we need to perform *case analysis* on b , using a `match` expression:

```

Definition negate_negate: forall (b: bool), Equals bool (negate (negate b)) b :=
fun (b: bool) =>
match b as B return Equals bool (negate (negate B)) B with
  true => equals_ bool true
| false => equals_ bool false
end.

```

This definition is accepted by Coq, i.e. this proof succeeds. By using the combination of an `as` clause and a `return` clause, we can substitute `true` resp. `false` for b in the return type (i.e. the proof goal) for the purpose of type-checking the first, resp. the second branch of the `match` expression. Since `negate (negate true)` reduces to `true`, Coq considers the types `Equals bool (negate (negate true)) true` and `Equals bool true true` to be equal.

When given a proof of an equality, one can use it to rewrite the goal. We prove symmetry of equality:

```

Definition symm(A: Type)(x y: A)(xy: Equals A x y): Equals A y x :=
match xy in Equals _ _ Y return Equals A Y x with

```

```

    equals_ => equals_ A x
  end.

```

Thanks to the **in** and **return** clauses introduced in Section 6, inside the **match** expression the goal becomes `Equals A x x`, which is proved directly using the constructor.

9 Inductive proofs

Let us now try to prove that concatenating an empty string to the end of a string does nothing:

```
forall (s: string), Equals string (concat s EmptyString) s

```

We will need to perform case analysis on `s` so that Coq can reduce the `concat` call, which performs a **match** expression on its first argument. We get two branches. The `EmptyString` branch is dealt with trivially. In the `NonemptyString` branch, the goal becomes

```
Equals string (concat (NonemptyString b s') EmptyString) (NonemptyString b s')

```

This reduces to

```
Equals string (NonemptyString b (concat s' EmptyString)) (NonemptyString b s')

```

At this point, we can finish the proof if only we can use the fact that `concat s' EmptyString` equals `s'`. But this is exactly what we are proving. Fortunately, `s'` was used as an argument in the constructor call used to construct `s`; therefore, we can use the fixpoint operator introduced in the section on recursive datatypes:

Definition `concat_EmptyString`:

```

forall (s: string), Equals string (concat s EmptyString) s :=
fix f(s: string) {struct s}: Equals string (concat s EmptyString) s :=
match s as S return Equals string (concat S EmptyString) S with
  EmptyString => equals_ string EmptyString
| NonemptyString b s' =>
  match f s' in Equals _ _ S'
  return Equals string (NonemptyString b (concat s' EmptyString)) (NonemptyString b S')
with
  equals_ => equals_ string (NonemptyString b (concat s' EmptyString))
end
end.

```

Notice that this proof has the structure of an inductive proof: there is a base case and an inductive step. In the inductive step, we have access to an induction hypothesis, in the form of the recursive call.

10 Inductively defined predicates

A concept that is pervasive in formal systems is the notion of an inductively defined predicate, also known as an inductively defined judgment/relation/set. In conventional terminology, such a predicate is defined by a set of *axioms* and *inference rules*, specifying the ways in which instances of the predicate can be constructed or *derived*. Inference rules differ from axioms in that the latter have *premises* and the former do not. Premises may themselves be instances of the predicate or not. (Often, premises that are not instances of the predicate themselves are called *side conditions* and rules that have side conditions only are considered to be axioms.)

For example, the less-than-or-equal-to relation on natural numbers can be defined inductively as follows (in the conventional inference rule notation):

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{LE-REFL} \\
 n \leq n
 \end{array}
 \qquad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{LE-SUCC} \\
 \frac{m \leq n}{m \leq n + 1}
 \end{array}$$

Note: the free variables in an axiom or inference rule are implicitly universally quantified. In other words, there is a separate instance of the rule for each instantiation of the free variables of a rule.

Given such a definition, a particular argument list satisfies the predicate if and only if a *derivation tree* (or *proof tree*) can be built whose root is the predicate applied to this argument list. A derivation tree is a finite tree where each node is labeled by an instance of the predicate which 1) matches an instance of an axiom or 2) matches the conclusion of an instance of an inference rule, and where for each (non-side-condition) premise of the instance of the inference rule, the node has a child whose label matches the premise.

For example, here is a derivation tree for the proposition $0 \leq 2$:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{0 \leq 0} \text{LE-REFL}}{0 \leq 1} \text{LE-SUCC}}{0 \leq 2} \text{LE-SUCC}}$$

The conventional concept of an inductively defined predicate corresponds exactly to a Coq parameterized datatype interpreted as a proposition via the Curry-Howard correspondence. Each axiom and each inference rule corresponds to a constructor of the datatype.

For example, the definition of the less-than-or-equal-to relation is as follows:

```
Inductive Le: nat -> nat -> Type :=
  le_refl: forall (n: nat), Le n n
| le_succ: forall (m n: nat), Le m n -> Le m (succ n).
```

The free variables and the premises of a rule correspond to the parameters of the constructor.

A derivation tree corresponds exactly to a value built from the constructors of the datatype. For example, here is a proof of `Le zero two`:

```
Definition Le_zero_two: Le zero two :=
  le_succ zero one
  (le_succ zero zero
   (le_refl zero)).
```

To prove a property of an inductively defined predicate, one typically performs *induction on the size of the derivation tree* (or, for short, *induction on the derivation*). This corresponds in Coq with structural recursion on the proof of the predicate instance using the fixpoint operator that we saw before. For example, here is a proof of the property $m \leq n \Rightarrow m + 1 \leq n + 1$:

```
Fixpoint Le_succ_succ(m n: nat)(H: Le m n) {struct H}: Le (succ m) (succ n) :=
  match H in Le M N return Le (succ M) (succ N) with
    le_refl n0 =>
      (* Goal: Le (succ n0) (succ n0) *)
      le_refl (succ n0)
  | le_succ m0 n0 H0 =>
      (* Goal: Le (succ m0) (succ (succ n0)) *)
      le_succ (succ m0) (succ n0) (Le_succ_succ m0 n0 H0)
  end.
```

11 Coq versus classical logic

Coq's built-in logic, whose essence was presented above, lacks some properties that are occasionally very useful. The main one is undoubtedly the law of the excluded middle: `forall (P: Type), Or P (Not P)`. In Coq terms, this proposition states that for any type, either it is inhabited or a function exists from that type to `False`, a manifestly uninhabited type. This and other propositions that are true in classical logic, and consistent with Coq's own logic, but not provided by it, can be declared as axioms:

```
Axiom excluded_middle: forall (P: Type), Or P (Not P).
```

This axiom enables a very important proof technique: proof by contradiction.⁴

Another useful axiom is functional extensionality, the principle that if two functions are pointwise equal, then they are equal:⁵

```
Axiom fun_ext:
  forall (A B: Type)(f g: A -> B),
  (forall (x: A), Equals B (f x) (g x)) ->
  Equals (A -> B) f g.
```

A third useful axiom is the axiom of choice, stating that if a relation is total (i.e. it relates each value to some value) then it defines a function.⁶

```
Axiom choice:
  forall (A B: Type)(R: A -> B -> Type),
  (forall (x: A), Exists B (R x)) ->
  Exists (A -> B) (fun (f: A -> B) => forall (x: A), R x (f x)).
```

12 Limitations of the Curry-Howard correspondence

It should be clear from the preceding sections that the Curry-Howard correspondence is very powerful: a proof system for a very large subset of classical logic can be obtained by interpreting programming language types as propositions and programs as proofs. However, the correspondence has its limitations: not all of classical logic can be obtained this way. In the previous section, we saw some properties of classical logic that are not provided by the correspondence, but that can be introduced as axioms. However, there are other properties of classical logic that are *inconsistent* with the correspondence.

12.1 Propositions about propositions

We encounter one such inconsistency when we consider propositions about propositions, i.e. propositions that quantify over propositions. For example, consider the proposition that states that for any proposition P , P implies $P \wedge P$. In Coq, we can state and prove this proposition as follows:

```
Definition P0: Type := forall (P: Type), P -> And P P.
```

```
Definition P0proof: P0 :=
  fun (P: Type) =>
  fun (p: P) =>
  and_ P P p p.
```

So far, so good. However, we should now be able to apply this theorem to itself to obtain the property

$$(\forall P. P \rightarrow P \wedge P) \wedge (\forall P. P \rightarrow P \wedge P)$$

as follows:

```
Definition AndPOP0proof: And P0 P0 := P0proof P0 P0proof.
(* Error: Universe inconsistency. *)
```

Unfortunately, Coq refuses to accept this definition; it complains that this definition would create a universe inconsistency.

To understand this error message, recall that our statement that the type of a type is `Type` was a little white lie: in fact, there is an infinite hierarchy of sorts `Type(0)`, `Type(1)`, `Type(2)`, etc., and the type of a given type is as follows:

⁴This axiom appears in module `Classical_Prop` in the Coq standard library with `P: Prop` instead of `P: Type`. It seems fine to use `P: Type` here, but use at your own risk.

⁵This axiom appears in module `FunctionalExtensionality`.

⁶This axiom appears in module `ClassicalEpsilon` with `R: A -> B -> Prop`.

- The type of a datatype is the maximum of the types of the parameter types of the constructors (not including the fixed datatype parameters).
- The type of a function type is the maximum of the type of the parameter type and the type of the result type.
- The type of a sort `Type(k)` is `Type(k+1)`.

Coq does not require or allow us to write these indices ourselves; it infers them automatically such that the abovementioned *universe constraints* are satisfied. If it cannot, it reports a *universe inconsistency*.

In the example, let k be the index of the type of parameter P in $P0$. Then the type of `And P P` is `Type(k)`, and the type of $P0$ is `Type(k+1)`. As a result, since `P0proof` takes only values of type `Type(k)` as an argument, it cannot accept $P0$.

Why does Coq impose these constraints? What is wrong with a system where there is one sort `Type` that is the type of all types? The answer is that such a system is inconsistent: it allows expressions to be constructed of any type whatsoever, including `False`.

Indeed, assume that there is one sort `Type` which is the type of all types. Then we can prove `False` as follows.⁷ We will encode naive set theory and then exploit Russell's paradox to obtain `False`. First, we define the universe U of all sets:

Inductive `U := set(I: Type)(P: I -> Type)(f: I -> U).`

Definition `In(x X: U): Type :=`
`match X with`
`set I P f => Exists I (fun i => And (P i) (Equals U (f i) x))`
`end.`

The proposition `In x X` encodes $x \in X$. Note that the above definitions are perfectly valid in Coq; they do not violate any universe constraints.

We can now define sets by specification:

Definition `id(x: U): U := x.`

Definition `spec(P: U -> Type): U := set U P id.`

Definition `spec_intro(P: U -> Type)(x: U)(H: P x): In x (spec P) :=`
`exists_ U (fun (i: U) => And (P i) (Equals U (id i) x))`
`x (and_ (P x) (Equals U (id x) x) H (equals_ U (id x) x)).`

Definition `spec_elim(P: U -> Type)(x: U)(H: In x (spec P)): P x :=`
`match H with exists_ i H0 =>`
`match H0 with and_ H1 H2 =>`
`match H2 in Equals _ _ X return P X with equals_ =>`
`H1`
`end end end.`

We proved that `In x (spec P)` if and only `P x`, for all sets x . Note that the definition of `spec` would trigger a universe inconsistency error in Coq.

We can now easily derive `False` by considering the set R of all sets that do not contain themselves:

Definition `PR(x: U): Type := Not (In x x).`

Definition `R: U := spec PR.`

Definition `contradiction(P: Type)(H1: Not P -> P)(H2: P -> Not P): False :=`
`(fun (H3: Not P) => H3 (H1 H3)) (fun (HP: P) => H2 HP HP).`

Definition `absurd: False := contradiction (In R R) (spec_intro PR R) (spec_elim PR R).`

The abovementioned universe constraints enable an interpretation of a type as the set of its values and a function as the set of its argument-result pairs in set theory: the interpretation of a type can be defined by

⁷Based on a proof by Paolo Capriotti.

recursing on the universe index and then on the structure of the type. Allowing `Type : Type` would preclude such an interpretation since this would mean that the interpretation of type `Type` contains itself, which is not possible in standard set theory.

12.2 Proof irrelevance

Another such inconsistency appears when we want to define *subset types*, i.e. types consisting of values that satisfy some property.

For example, we could define the integers as the pairs of natural numbers where at least one is zero:

```
Inductive Z :=
  z_(a b: nat)(H: Or (Equals nat a zero) (Equals nat b zero)).
```

Positive and negative 1 have the following representation in Z:

```
Definition pos1: Z :=
  z_ one zero
  (or_right (Equals nat one zero) (Equals nat zero zero) (equals_ nat zero)).
```

```
Definition neg1: Z :=
  z_ zero one
  (or_left (Equals nat zero zero) (Equals nat one zero) (equals_ nat zero)).
```

Is Z isomorphic with \mathbb{Z} ? Unfortunately, no: there are two distinct representations of the number zero:

```
Definition zero1: Z :=
  z_ zero zero
  (or_left (Equals nat zero zero) (Equals nat zero zero) (equals_ nat zero)).
```

```
Definition zero2: Z :=
  z_ zero zero
  (or_right (Equals nat zero zero) (Equals nat zero zero) (equals_ nat zero)).
```

Notice that `zero1` and `zero2` differ only in their third argument: the proof that at least one of the constituent natural numbers is zero. To show that these two values are indeed considered to be distinct by Coq, we can define a function that distinguishes them:

```
Definition is_zero1(z: Z): bool :=
  match z with
    z_ zero zero (or_left _) => true
  | _ => false
  end.
```

```
Definition zero1_is_zero1: Equals bool (is_zero1 zero1) true :=
  equals_ bool true.
```

```
Definition zero2_is_not_zero1: Equals bool (is_zero1 zero2) false :=
  equals_ bool false.
```

In order to facilitate the definition of subset types like Z in which appropriate equalities hold, we would like to have *proof irrelevance*: two proofs of the same proposition are considered equal. It would be tempting to introduce this property as an axiom; however, without some means to distinguish types used as propositions from types whose values have information content, such an axiom would be inconsistent.

12.3 Propositional extensionality

In classical logic, two propositions that are both true or both false can be considered equal. For example, in classical logic we have $\text{True} \vee \text{True} = \text{True}$. However, in Coq we have `Not (Equals Type (Or True True) True)`: `Or True True` is a type of two elements (`or_left True True true_` and `or_right True True true_`) whereas `True` is a type of one element (`true_`). The proof follows:

```
Definition singleton(A: Type): Type := forall (a b: A), Equals A a b.
```

```

Definition True_singleton: singleton True :=
  fun (p q: True) =>
  match p as P return Equals True P q with
  true_ =>
    match q as Q return Equals True true_ Q with
    true_ =>
      equals_ True true_
    end
  end
end.

```

```

Definition Not_Or_True_True_singleton: Not (singleton (Or True True)) :=
  fun (p: singleton (Or True True)) =>
  match
  match p (or_left True True true_) (or_right True True true_) in Equals _ _ B
  return match B with or_left _ => True | or_right _ => False end
  with
  equals_ => true_
  end
return False with end.

```

```

Definition Not_Equals_Or_True_True_True: Not (Equals Type (Or True True) True) :=
  fun (p: Equals Type (Or True True) True) =>
  match p in Equals _ _ B return Not (singleton B) with
  equals_ => Not_Or_True_True_singleton
  end
  True_singleton.

```

13 Beyond Curry-Howard: sort Prop

To address the limitations identified in the preceding section, Coq provides a means to allow the user to distinguish between types whose values have informational value on the one hand, and types used as propositions on the other hand: the latter types should be declared to be of sort **Prop**. For example:

```

Inductive AndP(P Q: Prop): Prop := andp_(p: P)(q: Q).
Inductive OrP(P Q: Prop): Prop := orp_left(p: P) | orp_right(q: Q).
Inductive EqualsP(A: Type)(a: A): A -> Prop := equalsp_: EqualsP A a a.
Inductive TrueP: Prop := truep_.
Inductive FalseP: Prop :=.

```

13.1 The elimination restriction

Coq enforces that values of types of sort **Prop** are not used for their informational content by imposing an *elimination restriction*: if a **match** expression matches on a value of a type of sort **Prop**, the return type of the **match** expression must itself also be of sort **Prop**. In other words, matching on proofs is allowed only to build other proofs.⁸ For example:

```

Definition is_orp_left(P Q: Prop)(H: OrP P Q): Prop :=
  match H with
  orp_left _ => TrueP
  | orp_right _ => FalseP
  end.

```

⁸An exception is if the type being matched on has just a single constructor and this constructor's parameter types are themselves of sort **Prop**. Such types have no informational content anyway.

```

(*)
Error:
Incorrect elimination of "H" in the inductive type "OrP":
the return type has sort "Type" while it should be "Prop".
Elimination of an inductive object of sort Prop
is not allowed on a predicate in sort Type
because proofs can be eliminated only to build proofs.
*)

```

Thanks to this restriction, a type of sort **Prop** can be interpreted in set theory as either the empty set (if the type is uninhabited) or a singleton set containing a canonical universal proof object (if the type is inhabited). The value of a **match** expression that matches on a proof is always simply this universal proof object.

As a result, the limitations identified in the preceding section do not hold for sort **Prop**.

13.2 Benefits

It is possible to apply propositions about propositions to themselves:

Definition POP: Prop := forall (P: Prop), P -> And P P.

Definition POPproof: POP :=
fun (P: Prop) =>
fun (p: P) =>
and_ P P p p.

Definition AndPPOPPOPproof: AndP POP POP := POPproof POP POPproof.

This typechecks because if the result type of a function type is of sort **Prop**, then the function type itself is of sort **Prop**.

We can define subset types with appropriate equalities⁹:

Inductive ZP :=
zp_(a b: nat)(H: OrP (EqualsP nat a zero) (EqualsP nat b zero)).

Definition one := succ zero.

Definition pos1: ZP :=
zp_ one zero
(orp_right (EqualsP nat one zero) (EqualsP nat zero zero) (equalsp_ nat zero)).

Definition neg1: ZP :=
zp_ zero one
(orp_left (EqualsP nat zero zero) (EqualsP nat one zero) (equalsp_ nat zero)).

Definition zero1: ZP :=
zp_ zero zero
(orp_left (EqualsP nat zero zero) (EqualsP nat zero zero) (equalsp_ nat zero)).

Definition zero2: ZP :=
zp_ zero zero
(orp_right (EqualsP nat zero zero) (EqualsP nat zero zero) (equalsp_ nat zero)).

Axiom proof_irrelevance: forall (P: Prop)(p q: P), EqualsP P p q.

Definition EqualsP_zero1_zero2: EqualsP ZP zero1 zero2 :=
match
proof_irrelevance
(OrP (EqualsP nat zero zero) (EqualsP nat zero zero))
(orp_left (EqualsP nat zero zero) (EqualsP nat zero zero) (equalsp_ nat zero))
(orp_right (EqualsP nat zero zero) (EqualsP nat zero zero) (equalsp_ nat zero))

⁹This axiom is available in the Coq standard library in module ProofIrrelevance.

```

in EqualsP _ _ Q return EqualsP ZP zero1 (zp_ zero zero Q)
with
  equalsp_ => equalsp_ ZP zero1
end.

```

We can perform equational reasoning on propositions:

Axiom propext: forall (P Q: Prop), (P -> Q) -> (Q -> P) -> EqualsP P Q.

13.3 Relaxing the elimination restriction

The **Prop** elimination restriction generally does not cause difficulties in practice. There are, however, a few exceptions. One is that we sometimes want to define a function by case splitting on the truth or falsehood of a proposition. For example, here is an attempt to define function update:

$$f[x := y] = \lambda a. \begin{cases} y & \text{if } a = x \\ f(a) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Axiom excluded_middle: forall (P: Prop), OrP P (NotP P).

```

Definition update(A B: Type)(f: A -> B)(x: A)(y: B): A -> B :=
fun (a: A) =>
match excluded_middle (EqualsP A a x) with
  orp_left _ => y
| orp_right _ => f x
end.

```

(* *Error: Incorrect elimination of "excluded_middle (EqualsP A a x)" ... **)

There are two possible solutions. One solution is to develop a decision procedure for the proposition (i.e. an expression of type **bool** instead of type **Prop**). Another is to use a version of the axiom of excluded middle where the disjunction is in **Type** rather than in **Prop**¹⁰:

Axiom excluded_middle_informative: forall (P: Prop), Or P (NotP P).

```

Definition update(A B: Type)(f: A -> B)(x: A)(y: B): A -> B :=
fun (a: A) =>
match excluded_middle_informative (EqualsP A a x) with
  or_left _ => y
| or_right _ => f x
end.

```

```

Definition update_test: EqualsP nat (update nat nat succ zero zero zero) zero :=
match excluded_middle_informative (EqualsP nat zero zero) as E
return
  EqualsP nat
  (match E with or_left _ => zero | or_right _ => succ zero end) zero
with
  or_left _ =>
    equalsp_ nat zero
| or_right H =>
  match H (equalsp_ nat zero) return EqualsP nat (succ zero) zero with end
end.

```

¹⁰This axiom is available in module `ClassicalEpsilon` in the Coq standard library.

Another place where one bumps into the elimination restriction is when one wishes to define a function by indefinite description. For example:

```

Definition get_witness(T: Type)(P: T -> Prop)(e: ExistsP T P): T :=
  match e with
    existsp_ t p => t
  end.
(* Error: Incorrect elimination of "e" ... *)

```

Again, there are two possible solutions. One solution is to develop an algorithm that computes a witness. Another is to use an axiom that converts an existence proof in `Prop` to one in `Type`¹¹:

```

Axiom constructive_indefinite_description:
  forall (T: Type)(P: T -> Prop), ExistsP T P -> Exists T P.

```

```

Definition get_witness(T: Type)(P: T -> Prop)(e: ExistsP T P): T :=
  match constructive_indefinite_description T P e with
    exists_ t p => t
  end.

```

13.4 Subtyping

Notice that something strange is happening in the expressions above. In the statement of axiom `excluded_middle_informative`, we pass `P` and `NotP P` as arguments to `Or`, even though `Or`'s parameters are of type `Type` and `P` and `NotP P` are of type `Prop`. Similarly, in the statement of axiom `constructive_indefinite_description`, we are passing `P` as an argument to `Exists`. What is going on here is a form of *subtyping*: any type is of type `Type`, even if it is also of type `Prop`. That is, `Prop` is a subtype of `Type`. And in fact, the type of `Prop` itself is `Type(1)`.

14 The sort Set

In addition to the hierarchy of `Type` sorts and the sort `Prop`, Coq has the sort `Set`. As far as this author can see, `Set` is simply a way to write `Type(0)`. It is therefore not really a distinct sort. The type of `Set` is `Type(1)`. From the fact that `Set` is simply `Type(0)`, it follows that `Set` is the type of the “small” datatypes and function types, i.e. the ones whose values do not directly or indirectly involve types.

It seems to be the case that for any Coq file that mentions `Set` and that verifies, if one replaces all occurrences of `Set` with `Type` the file still verifies. Therefore, the notation `Set` seems to be superfluous. Reasons why it exists nonetheless may be the following: 1) historical/compatibility: perhaps old versions of Coq had `Set` but not `Type`; 2) there is a command line option that makes `Set` impredicative, but not `Type`; 3) it may have (probably very minor) performance and simplicity benefits since using `Set` instead of `Type` avoids the introduction of universe level variables and constraints.

Note: It does not seem to be the case that expressions of types of sort `Set` are treated differently from expressions of types of sort `Type` by the extraction mechanism (that translates Coq definitions to the programming language OCaml). Indeed, many expressions that should be, and are, extracted successfully are of types of sort `Type(k)` with $k > 0$, e.g. type-generic functions such as list concatenation.

15 Conclusion

You are now in a position where you can see how a wide variety of theory developments (definitions and proofs) can in principle be formalised in Coq. The main intended results to take away from reading this text are an understanding and an appreciation of precise, rigorous reasoning: simple rules can be given for the form and validity of an argument or line of reasoning.

¹¹This axiom, too, is available in module `ClassicalEpsilon` in the Coq standard library.

This text did not introduce the many features that Coq offers to facilitate the definition of concepts (type inference, implicit arguments, notations, sections, modules, etc.) or the interactive construction of proofs (proof scripts, the tactic language, automation, reflection, etc.) or the extraction of programs into an industrial-strength programming language like OCaml. It also did not introduce the many concepts available in the Coq standard library. Finally, it did not present all details of Coq's logic, the Calculus of Inductive Constructions; missing elements include mutually recursive datatypes and functions, and coinductive datatypes and functions. For more information on all of these, see the Coq website, or the books by Yves Bertot, Benjamin Pierce, or Adam Chlipala.